

Comparative Assessment of Water Purification Techniques Awareness and Socio-Economic Variabilities among Household Owners in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper assessed water purification techniques awareness and socio-economic variabilities among household owners in Zamfara state, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Population for this study was 592,106 household owners in Zamfara state. Sample size of 384 household owners were selected using multistage sampling procedures which include cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling. Questionnaire on comparative assessment of water purification techniques awareness and socio-economic variabilities among household owners was used and validated by five (5) experts, the instrument was pilot-tested using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. SPSS version 25 was used for data analysis where descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions and inferential statistics to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara state is significant ($p=0.000$); socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara state is significant ($p=0.000$). Based on the results, the study concluded that household owners in Zamfara State possess significant awareness of water purification methods which are influenced by socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation. Based on the conclusion, the study recommended that Zamfara State Water Board implement community-led water purification education programs, the Zamfara State government provide subsidies or incentives for purification tools.

Keyword: Knowledge, Water purification, socioeconomic variables, Household;

Introduction

The size and capacity of water treatment systems vary widely ranging from simple households units to small facilities that serve manufacturing industries to large scale centralized water treatment plants dedicated to cities and towns. Selection of specific treatment processes depends upon factors such as intake water quality, degree of purification required, intended water use, flow capacity requirements, government regulations, available capital and the operations as well as maintenance costs involved (Centre for Disease Control, 2022). Water contamination is primarily caused by the discharge of untreated wastewater from enterprises. The effluent or sewage discharge from various enterprises which contains varying levels of contaminants is dumped into rivers or other water sources. The wastewater may have a high proportion of organic and inorganic contaminants at the initial discharge. Industries generate waste water as a result of fabrication processes, processes dealing with paper and pulp, textiles, chemicals and from various streams such as cooling towers, boilers and production lines (Singh, et al, 2018).

Treatment for drinking water production involves the removal of contaminants and/or inactivation of any potentially harmful microbes from raw water to produce water that is pure enough for human consumption without any short term or long term risk of any adverse health effect. In general terms, the greatest microbial risks are associated with ingestion of water that is contaminated with human or animal (including bird) faeces. Faeces can be a source of pathogenic bacteria, viruses, protozoa and helminths (WHO, 2020).

Objective of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess awareness of water purification techniques and socio-economic variabilities among household owners in Zamfara state. Therefore, the study will be guided by the following specific objectives, to:

1. Assess awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State;
2. Assess socio economic determinants of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the level of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State?
2. What are the socio-economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara state?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. **H₀₁**: Awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant;
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Methodology

Descriptive research design was used for this study. According to Shields and Rangarajan, (2013), descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It does not answer questions about how/when/why the characteristics occurred. Rather it addresses "what" question (what are the characteristics of the population or situation being studied). Descriptive research design focuses on the people and their beliefs, opinions, perception and behaviors (Nwana, 2015).

The population of this study comprise of five hundred and ninety-two thousands, one hundred and six (592,106) household owners from all fourteen (14) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Zamfara State. This is based on the data obtained on Distribution of Households by Type of Housing Unit from the National Population Commission (NPC, 2020), Zamfara State office, Gusau.

A sample size of three hundred and eighty-four (384) Households was participated in the study. This is based on the sample size selection table by Research Advisors (2006), which suggests that for a population of 592,106 a sample size of 384 is sufficient for generalization at a 95% confidence level and at 5.0% margin of error. Multistage sampling technique was used by the researcher that comprises of cluster, proportionate and systematic sampling which Alvi (2016), explained that, this type of sampling technique were used when the elements of the population are more than one and spread. Cluster sampling technique was used by the researcher to group or to divide the state based on three (3) senatorial zones (i.e Zamfara central, north and west).

A proportionate sampling technique was used to select one (1) Local Government (Gusau) from Zamfara central, One (1) Local Government (kaura Namoda) from Zamfara north and 2 Local Government (Talata Mafara & Gummi) from Zamfara west senatorial zone. Thus, Zamfara central has only four (4) Local Governments, Zamfara north also has four (4) local governments while Zamfara west has (6) Local Governments respectively. In order to be fair to the population distribution, the research chooses two (2) Local Government from Zamfara west and one (1) each from Zamfara north and Zamfara central zones.

A proportionate sampling procedure was adopted to compose the sample size of 384 among the four (4) selected Local Government Areas where Gusau has 130 numbers of respondents, Kaura Namoda 100, Talata Mafara 78, and Gummi 76. Which Sulaiman (2015), explained that proportionate sampling is used when the elements of the populations vary considerably in size because, it assures that those in larger size will have the same probability of getting the larger sample size as those in the smaller size will get the small sample and systematic sampling was used for selection of households on the basis of numerical sequence.

Table 1: Sample Size Distribution

S/N	Senatorial Districts	Sampled Local Gov't Areas	Sampled Households
1.	Zamfara Central	Gusau	130
2.	Zamfara-North	Kaura-Namoda	100

3.	Zamfara-West	Talata-Mafara	78
		Gummi	76
Total	03	04	384

A questionnaire titled “Comparative Assessment of Water Purification Techniques Awareness and Socio-economic Variabilities of Household Owners” (CAWPTASVHO) was developed by the researcher. The questionnaire is made in two parts, A and B. Part A obtained the information of households socio demographic characteristics, parts B obtained households information on awareness of water purification techniques using Multi Choice Questions (MCQ) with option a, b, c and d through a rating scale of highly knowledgeable (70% to 100%), knowledgeable (60% to 69%), moderately (50% to 59%) and not knowledgeable (50% and below),

The instrument was subjected and validated by 5 experts who scrutinized the instrument were suggestions and corrections were incorporated in the final draft.

The validated instrument was subjected to reliability test using cronbach Alpha to test the internal consistency via statistical package for social science (SPSS) and reliability level of 0.89 was obtained.

An introductory letter from the Head of Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was to obtain by the researcher to enable him collect data from the sampled households, where 384 questionnaires were duly distributed to 384 households through their consent by the researcher with the help of three (3) research assistants and 384 questionnaires was retrieved.

For the analysis of the data that was collected from the household owners, the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 25 was used to analyze the data obtained from the respondents. The demographic characteristics of respondents were computed using frequency and percentage. Research question 1 was answered using frequency and percentage, were research question 2 was answered using mean and standard deviation. One sample-t-test was used to test Hypotheses 1 on awareness of water purification while multiple regression analysis was used to test hypothesis 2 on socio economic determinants of water purification techniques of household owners in Zamfara state. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

All data collected on demographic characteristics of the respondents were tabulated using frequencies and percentages as indicated in Table 2

Table 2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Range in Years		
18 – 40	240	62.5
40 and above	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	297	77.3
Female	87	22.7
Total	384	100.0
Income		
Less than 30,000	89	23.2
30,000 to 50,000	167	43.5
50,000 to 100,000	80	20.8
More than 100,000	48	12.5
Total	384	100.0
Educational Qualification		
Primary	14	3.6
Secondary	64	16.7
Tertiary	288	75.0
Non Formal	18	4.7
Total	384	100.0
Occupation		
Civil Servant	237	61.7

Business Man	81	21.1
Farmers	36	9.4
Others	30	7.8
Total	384	100.0

Table 2: provides the demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. The data is presented across three variables: age range in years, gender, income, educational qualification and occupation, with corresponding frequencies and percentages. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents 62.5%, (240 respondents) were between 18 and 40 years old, while 37.5% (144 respondents) were 40 years and above. The gender composition of the sample was predominantly male, with 77.3% (297 respondents) being men and 22.7% (87 respondents) being women.

Regarding income levels, the largest group of respondents 43.5%, (167 respondents) reported earning between 30,000 to 50,000 Nigerian Naira, The second largest income group was those earning less than 30,000 Naira, accounting for 23.2% (89 respondents). 20.8% (80 respondents) reported earning between 50,000 to 100,000 Naira, while the smallest group (12.5%, 48 respondents) earned more than 100,000 Naira.

Educational qualifications of the respondents showed that the vast majority 75%, (288 respondents) had tertiary education. Secondary education was the next most common, with 16.7% (64 respondents). Only 3.6% (14 respondents) had primary education, while 4.7% (18 respondents) had non-formal education.

In terms of occupation, civil servants constituted the largest group, representing 61.7% (237 respondents) of the sample. Businessmen made up 21.1% (81 respondents), while farmers accounted for 9.4% (36 respondents). The remaining 7.8% (30 respondents) were classified under "Others" for their occupation.

Research Question One: What is the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State?

Table 3: (a) Item by item Analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

S/N	Awareness of Water Purification	Frequency	Percent
1	Which of the following methods is used for water purification?		
	Separation	105	27.3
	Filtration	190	49.5
	Inoculation	2	0.5
	All of the above	87	22.7
	Total	384	100.0
2	Which of the following statements is true?		
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can lead to the consumption of contaminated water	173	45.1
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can provide clean and safe drinking water	80	20.8
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can cause no harmful effect to well-being	31	8.1
	Inability to use any of the purification methods can prevent individuals from consumption of contaminated water	100	26.0
	Total	384	100.0
3	Consumption of contaminated water can expose individuals to the outbreak of waterborne diseases like:		
	Headache	8	2.1
	Diarrhea	294	76.6
	Cancer	26	6.8
	All of the above	56	14.6
	Total	384	100.0
4	Contaminants can be reduced or totally removed out of water through:		
	Water harvesting	64	16.7
	Water production	70	18.2
	Water raining	59	15.4

	Water purification	191	49.7
	Total	384	100.0
5	Access to purified drinking water can improve the:		
	Quality of life	302	78.6
	Walking standard	19	4.9
	Intellectual ability	45	11.7
	None of the above	18	4.7
	Total	384	100.0
6	Life-threatening worms that can be prevented through the use of purified water include the following except:		
	Dracunculiasis	48	12.5
	Schistosomiasis	95	24.7
	Filariasis	70	18.2
	Trachoma	171	44.5
	Total	384	100.0
7	Additives used to improve the quality of water include:		
	Aluminium sulphate (Alum)	190	49.5
	Chlorine	96	25.0
	Calcium hypochlorite	16	4.2
	All of the above	82	21.4
	Total	384	100.0
8	The most effective method of disinfection of pathogenic organisms in water is through:		
	Filtration	85	22.1
	Sedimentation	51	13.3
	Coagulation	15	3.9
	Boiling	233	60.7
	Total	384	100.0
9	Use of filters is very important and crucial in water purification because:		
	It helps to remove contaminants out of the water	308	80.2
	It helps to add contaminants into the water	37	9.6
	It helps attract debris into the water	25	6.5
	None of the above	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0
10	The major cause of waterborne diseases is:		
	Surface water	50	13.0
	Rainwater	26	6.8
	Open defecation and urination	294	76.6
	Borehole water	14	3.6
	Total	384	100.0

Table 3 (a) presents the awareness of water purification techniques of household owners in Zamfara State. Regarding purification methods, nearly half 49.5%, (n=190) of respondents identified filtration, while 27.3% (n=105) chose separation, and 22.7% (n=87) selected all methods including inoculation, which was chosen by only 0.5% (n=2). When asked about the implications of not using purification methods, 45.1% (n=173) correctly recognized that it could lead to consuming contaminated water, while 26% (n=100) incorrectly believed it would prevent contaminated water consumption. On waterborne diseases, the vast majority (76.6%, n=294) accurately identified diarrhoea as a potential outcome of consuming contaminated water.

Regarding contaminant removal, approximately half (49.7%, n=191) of the respondents correctly identified water purification as the solution. A significant majority (78.6%, n=302) recognized that access to purified drinking water could improve quality of life. On the topic of water-related diseases, 44.5% (n=171) incorrectly identified trachoma as not being preventable through purified water use. For water treatment additives, alum was the most recognized (49.5%, n=190), followed by chlorine (25%, n=96).

Concerning disinfection methods, 60.7% (n=233) correctly identified boiling as the most effective method for eliminating pathogenic organisms. The importance of filters was well understood, with 80.2% (n=308) correctly stating that filters help remove contaminants from water. Finally, regarding the major cause of waterborne diseases, more than three-quarters of respondents (76.6%, n=294) accurately identified open defecation and urination as the primary factor, while relatively few attributed it to surface water (13%, n=50), rainwater (6.8%, n=26), or borehole water (3.6%, n=14).

Table 3: (b) Respondent by Respondent Analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

S/N	Respondent Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Remark	Rating Scale
1	100%	19	4.95%	4.95%	Highly Knowledgeable
2	90%	45	11.72%	11.72%	
3	80%	55	14.32%	14.32%	
4	70%	93	24.22%	24.22%	
	Total			55.21%	
5	60%	54	14.06%	14.06%	Knowledgeable
6	50%	50	13.02%	13.02%	Moderate
7	40%	22	5.73%	5.73%	Not Knowledgeable
8	30%	22	5.73%	5.73%	
9	20%	10	2.6%	2.6%	
10	10%	14	3.65	3.65	
	Total			17.715	
	Grand Total	384	100%	100%	

Table 3 (b) present the summary of respondent by respondent analysis on awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state, in regard to these about 4.95%, (n=19) of the respondents scored 100%, 11.72% (n=45) scored 90%, 14.32% (n=55) scored 80% and 24.22% (n=93) scored 70%, and range indicated by rating scale for highly knowledgeable is between 70% to 100%. While 14.06% (n=54) that scored 60% are identified as knowledgeable, 13.02% (n=50) that scored 50% are moderate. Respondents that are classified as not knowledgeable are between the range of 49-10%, to about 5.73% (n=22) scored 40%, 5.73% (n=22) scored 30%, 2.6% (n=10) scored 20% and 3.65% (n=14) scored 10% respectively.

Research Question two: What are the socio economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State?

Table 4: Mean Score of responses on the socio economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference
Knowledge (Constant)	2.31	0.38	
Income	2.23	0.94	0.08
Educational Qualification	2.81	0.57	0.50
Occupation	1.63	0.94	0.68

Table 4: shows the mean score on the socio-economic determinants of awareness of household owners on water purification techniques in Zamfara State with a mean of 2.31, 2.23, 2.81 and 1.63 and mean difference of 0.08, 0.50 and 0.68. Based on this outcome, socio-economic factors (income, educational qualification and occupation) determine the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State.

Based on the research questions, the following hypotheses are formulated for this study.

Hypothesis One: Awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant

Table 5: One-Sample t-test Analysis of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	p-value
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Knowledge	384	2.30	0.38	383	118.697	0.000
Test Mean	384	2.50	0.00			

Calculated $p < 0.05$, calculated t -value > 1.972 at df 383

The result of the one-sample t-test statistics in Table 5 reveals that the awareness of water purification among household owners in Zamfara State is significant because the calculated p-value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance and the calculated t-value of 118.697 is higher than the 1.972 critical t-value at 383 degrees of freedom (df). Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is not significant was rejected. This means that members of household owners in Zamfara State have adequate awareness of water purification techniques.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in socio-economic determinants (income, education and occupation) of awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara state.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis on Awareness of Water Purification techniques and Socio-economic Variables

Model Summary					
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	
.113	.013	0.005	.38005	1.427	
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	.710	3	.237	1.639	.000
Residual	54.886	380	.144		
Total	55.597	383			
Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	2.033	.137		14.847	.000
Income	.026	.022	.064	1.187	.000
Educational Qualification	.051	.037	.076	1.358	.000
Occupation	.046	.023	.113	1.955	.000

Table 6 shows the outcome of multiple regression analysis on the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners and socio economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State. The overall model shows a statistically significant relationship ($F(3, 380) = 1.639, p < .005$), indicating that at least one of the predictors (income, educational qualification and occupation) has a significant influence on awareness of water purification techniques. However, the amount of variance explained by the model is relatively low, with an R-squared of 0.013, suggesting that only about 1.3% of the variability in the awareness of water purification techniques can be explained by these socio-economic variables.

Examining the individual predictors, income, educational qualification and occupation each have statistically significant relationships with awareness of water purification techniques. Specifically, income ($\beta = 0.064, p < .005$), educational qualification ($\beta = 0.076, p < .005$), and occupation ($\beta = 0.113, p < .005$) all positively influence awareness, as indicated by their positive standardized coefficients. Based on this outcome, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in awareness of water purification techniques among household owners on socio-economic variables (income, education and occupation) in Zamfara State was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding from the study revealed that awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that household owners in Zamfara State demonstrate a significant level of awareness about water purification techniques. The finding aligns with several previous studies, while also showing some differences compared to others.

The significant awareness found in this study is consistent with research by Miner, et al (2015) on household drinking water; knowledge and practice of purification in a community of Lamingo, Plateau State, Nigeria which reported that 26.1% of respondents had good knowledge of water purification, and 59.8% had fair knowledge. This affirmed that awareness and understanding of water purification methods may be relatively high across different regions of Nigeria. Similarly, Mustapha, et al (2022) conducted research on household awareness and practices on Water Sanitation and Hygiene (WASH) in an Arid Region of North western Nigeria, Sokoto State and found fairly good levels of WASH understanding in Sokoto State, an arid region neighboring Zamfara. This geographical proximity and similar environmental conditions may explain the comparable knowledge levels.

The finding from the study revealed that socio economic determinants (income, education and occupation) on awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State is significant ($p = 0.000$). This means that socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation significantly influence the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State. This result agrees with Miner et al. (2015), who found that knowledge of water purification was statistically significantly associated with the level of education among respondents in Lamingo, Plateau State. Those with higher education levels tended to have better knowledge of purification methods.

Similarly, Abera, et al (2020), observed in their study in rural Ethiopia that poor knowledge related to water, sanitation and hygiene were more common among residents with lower socio economic status. They noted that education level in particular had a significant influence on WASH knowledge and practices. The findings are also consistent with Rima et al. (2017), who reported a statistically significant difference in knowledge regarding water sanitation and hygiene based on mothers' education levels in rural Nepal. Those with higher education demonstrated better knowledge.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were made:

1. Household owners in Zamfara State demonstrate a significant level of awareness about water purification techniques.
2. Socio economic factors such as income, education, and occupation significantly influence the awareness of water purification techniques among household owners in Zamfara State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the study recommended the following:

1. The Zamfara State Water Board should leverage the existing awareness base by implementing community-led water purification education programmes.
2. The Zamfara State government should provide subsidies or incentives for water purification tools and products to encourage wider adoption of purification practices.

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